

Book of Abstracts

CASES III

Citizen Art-Science Engagement Strategies
2 JULY 2025, University of Pompeu Fabra-Barcellona (ES)

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The **CASES (Citizen Art-Science Engagement Strategies)** program, founded in Dublin in 2022 with the support of the Politecnico di Torino, began its activities hosted by the Italian Cultural Institute in Dublin (IIC–Ministry of Foreign Affairs). The program involves 10 international researchers and promotes an interdisciplinary approach where science, art, and civic engagement converge to address contemporary challenges and support the global goals of the UN 2030 Agenda. CASES creates collaborative spaces for co-producing knowledge, emphasizing creativity, community participation, and critical reflection. Through participatory practices, educational workshops, and artistic initiatives, the program fosters inclusion, empowerment, and social and ecological awareness, connecting citizens, students, researchers, and artists. This integrated approach transforms communities into living laboratories for learning and innovation, promoting a model of co-creation in which art, science, and civic engagement work together for sustainability and social cohesion.

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Visual Attention and Cognitive Control of Intentions

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<https://d-ferro.github.io>

Our brains constantly manage many thoughts and pieces of information at once.

To do this efficiently, the brain uses selective attention, focusing on what matters most while filtering out distractions. When we pay attention to something we see, areas of the brain responsible for processing vision boost their activity. This helps important information travel more effectively across brain regions. My previous work [1] shows that covert visual attention increases neural activity in high frequency ranges and strengthens communication between visual brain areas.

Decision-making relies on similar selective processes. When choosing between different options, especially when rewards are involved, the brain evaluates each possibility step by step before committing to a choice. Using a free viewing approach, recent work [2] shows that people often look directly at the options they value most. This behavior aligns with activity in areas of the brain that encode reward. Looking back at an option, even briefly, can reactivate its stored value in the brain, even when the option is no longer visible. Neurons that track value also appear to relate to upcoming actions, suggesting a close connection between what we pay attention to and what we intend to do. By studying how visual attention and eye movements shape decision-making, future work aims to uncover how selective focus influences both what we think and how we act.

1. D. Ferro, T. Cash-Padgett, M. Zhe-Wang, B. Y. Hayden, R. Moreno-Bote, *Gaze-centered gating, reactivation, and reevaluation of economic value in orbitofrontal cortex*, Nature Communications, 15:6163, 2024
2. D. Ferro, J. van Kempen, M. Boyd, S. Panzeri, A. Thiele, *Directed information exchange between cortical layers in macaque V1 and V4 and its modulation by selective attention*, PNAS, 118(12), e202297118, 2021

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Endangered Minorities, Vanishing Ecosystems: Strategies of Mutual Support within an Integrated Ecocultural Vision

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This paper presents the conceptual and methodological outcomes of the research project **MINOR ECHOES (Minority Ecocultural Heritage Relationalities)**, which investigates the mutual entanglement of environmental and cultural endangerment within minority contexts in Europe. Moving beyond a dualistic view that separates ecological and cultural loss, the project proposes an *integrated ecocultural perspective* that treats ecosystems and cultural systems as interdependent and co-constituted. Within this framework, the paper examines how collaborative and participatory approaches in anthropology can contribute to the broader goals of citizen science, community empowerment, and epistemic justice. At the core of this contribution lies the practice of **collaborative ethnography**, conceived as both a method and an ethical stance. Rather than positioning communities as objects of study, the research process is co-designed with local participants who act as *citizen scientists*, contributing personal narratives, ecological observations, linguistic data, and cultural insights. This co-production of knowledge challenges extractivist and hierarchical modes of research, foregrounding instead a dialogical model in which the authority of interpretation is shared and constantly negotiated. Through this, ethnography becomes a space of relational accountability, where knowledge is collectively created, situated, and used for transformative purposes. The paper further reflects on how such participatory methodologies foster **reciprocal forms of visibility and legitimacy**. By integrating scientific tools and community-based practices, collaborative anthropology can help generate data that are not only analytically rich but also politically effective, capable of informing local advocacy, environmental monitoring, and cultural revitalization efforts. The process itself thus becomes a strategy of mutual support between researchers and communities, aimed at strengthening both environmental resilience and cultural continuity. Ultimately, the paper argues for a redefinition of ethnographic engagement as a **citizen science of coexistence**, one that acknowledges the inseparability of human and ecological diversity. By aligning anthropological inquiry with grassroots activism and participatory knowledge production, the research advances a model of *ecocultural collaboration* where documentation, reflection, and resistance merge into a shared project of care for endangered worlds.

Humanism in Tourism: Participatory Approaches to Address Overtourism and Promote Livability. A Human Rights Practicum in Sorrento.

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Participatory practice within citizen science is essential for tackling the complex challenges of urban regeneration, climate change, and sustainable development, particularly in small and rural communities. As Robert Chambers (1997) insightfully noted, participatory engagement raises critical questions: “*Whose participation? How? When? And for what purpose?*” These questions remain central to ensuring equitable and inclusive approaches in urban regeneration. The Case for Participatory Practices : Participatory approaches shift decision-making from a top-down model to a hybrid, collaborative, and bidirectional process that emphasizes empowerment, equity, and collective transformation. By integrating co-design and co-creation methodologies, these approaches enhance the role of local stakeholders in fostering ownership, addressing community-specific issues, and shaping policies and programs that reflect their lived experiences.

Key benefits include:

1. Empowerment and equity: Active participation ensures urban policies are inclusive and mitigate unintended consequences such as green gentrification or urban polarization.
2. Knowledge sharing and collaboration: Citizen science fosters local data collection and knowledge exchange, bridging the gap between local initiatives and national/global sustainability frameworks, and supporting long-term sustainability and knowledge transfer.
3. Co-creation for transformation: Participatory research moves “*from research on people to research with people*” (Heron & Reason, 2006), fostering deeper collaboration, community ownership, and the capacity to innovate and advocate for change.

Addressing Challenges Through Citizen Science : Smaller cities often face challenges such as limited access to global knowledge networks and the stagnation of best-practice research, hindering effective urban regeneration. Citizen science and participatory practices can overcome these obstacles by:

- Supporting localized data collection to inform context-specific solutions.
- Promoting methodologies that empower communities to adopt sustainable practices.
- Creating cooperative inquiry platforms for collaboratively addressing systemic vulnerabilities.

Promoting Participatory Innovation: Innovative urban action requires collaboration among diverse stakeholders. Recent studies underscore the importance of participatory governance in cultural and creative industries, particularly in smaller and rural communities. Integrating participatory methods into policy development ensures that urban areas are better equipped to navigate the complexities of sustainable regeneration. Ultimately, participatory citizen science represents a powerful tool for democratizing urban regeneration and fostering innovative solutions to both global and local sustainability challenges.

EcoPoli, students of sustainability Valerio Giunta¹

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The presentation highlights the activities of the **Student Sustainability Hub** at Politecnico of Torino, with a particular focus on the initiatives of the student team **EcòPoli**. Founded in 2017 under the guidance of the Politecnico's Green Team, EcòPoli addresses sustainability in a comprehensive way, encompassing environmental, social, and energy aspects. The presentation will cover key team initiatives, including the introduction of **waste separation** at the university, **semesterly WEEE collections**, the **Sus PoliTalk** podcast, **Green Talks**, projects related to **Biochar** and **paper recycling**, and the launch event of the Student Sustainability Hub on **May 16, 2025**, along with upcoming projects and events. The focus is on the contribution of the student community to making the Politecnico more sustainable and enjoyable to live in, providing students the opportunity to actively shape a greener campus. The presentation will be delivered by **Valerio Giunta**, serving as EcòPoli's team leader for the third time, who will revisit the introduction from the **Carbon Footprint** event held at the Politecnico in 2023.

Figure 1: EcoPoli Students, Politecnico of Torino (Italy), Torino-Italy

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The Role of Art in Educational Processes and Community Regeneration: Perspectives for the CASES Program

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Contemporary art, when integrated into educational and community contexts, can become a powerful tool for cultural and environmental transformation. Within the European CASES program (Citizen Art-Science Engagement Strategies), we propose an approach that combines participatory artistic practices, sustainability education, and citizen science, with particular attention to the school community (Fig.1). Through the methodology of creative reuse of waste materials—developed in previous initiatives such as the S.R.A. Sound Reuse Artworks—we organize collective workshops in which students and citizens reflect on the environmental, economic, and social impacts of the production, transport, and disposal of the objects around them. The process includes the collection and analysis of materials, co-design of collective artworks, and co-creation of installations that reflect the environmental urgencies and values of the local area. Art thus becomes an informal educational language that interacts with science, connecting the local to the global and, in some way, making the invisible visible and tangible. The intervention aims to promote the sustainability competencies outlined by GreenComp (JRC – European Commission): empathy, responsibility, critical thinking, and care for the planet. In this way, schools transform into hubs for community regeneration, capable of fostering intercultural dialogues and transnational alliances, even in small or disadvantaged contexts (such as North Africa and the Balkans), where the CASES program is expanding. Strategic objectives include:

- Strengthening the educational impact of the CASES program on emotional, experiential, and symbolic levels;
- Leaving collective artworks as a cultural legacy for the community;
- Promoting networking among artists, educators, and researchers to develop replicable best practices.

In summary, art can act as a catalyst for learning, cohesion, and ecological awareness, contributing synergistically to the educational and transformative mission of CASES.

Figure 1: Recycled Rhythms: Inspiring Kids Through Music

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Youth Participatory Strategies and Planetary Boundaries: The Contribution of CASES and the PA-MAP Project to Ecological and Social Resilience

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The PA-MAP project (Participatory Approaches for Atmospheric Monitoring in Urban Environments), funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement n. 945380 and developed within the EUTOPIA network, engages students, teachers, families, and local communities to promote sustainability education and environmental awareness. Hosted by the University of Ljubljana and co-hosted by the Universitat Pompeu Fabra – Planetary Wellbeing Research Centre, PA-MAP integrates scientific research, education, and participatory practices to enhance ecological and social resilience in urban contexts. The project has involved over 400 students aged 9–10. Aligned with Sustainable Development Goals 3, 4, 11, and 13, PA-MAP implements experimental activities, educational workshops, and co-design processes to monitor air quality and other environmental parameters in schools and urban spaces. Through the **ORPAC** methodology (Observe, Reflect, Plan, Act, Change), students engage in systematic observation, critical reflection, practical interventions, and transformative actions, developing scientific literacy and civic responsibility. The project is currently active in four European cities, each with specific schools and activities. In Ljubljana, at Janeza Levca Primary School, continuous monitoring of particulate matter (PM₁, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀) in classrooms, cafeterias, and gyms allows evaluation of exposure gradients and supports mitigation strategies and urban planning. In Contursi Terme, at Vincenzo Lardo Primary School, a school botanical garden promotes biodiversity, outdoor environmental education, and the redevelopment of disused areas into educational and recreational spaces. In Turin, at Convitto Umberto I, thematic modules on air pollution raise awareness, enhance digital literacy, and encourage protective behaviors among students. In Barcelona, at Maria Montessori Primary School, hands-on workshops and co-design activities engage students on climate change and air quality issues, contributing to local adaptation strategies and the development of innovative educational tools, including a children's storybook. By integrating youth participation, scientific monitoring, and educational innovation, PA-MAP demonstrates how young people can actively contribute to urban sustainability, planetary health, and the creation of resilient communities, supporting the objectives of the CASES program.

Figure 1: PA-MAP activities at Malgrat de Mar, Barcelona (ES)

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Technological Humanism, Contemporary Art, and Visual Perception. Performance as a Perspective for Artistic-Scientific Research.

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This presentation explores the intersection of technological humanism, contemporary art, and visual perception, highlighting performance as a methodological and conceptual lens for artistic-scientific research. It investigates how creative practices can serve as experimental tools for understanding perception, cognition, and the interaction between human experience and technological environments.

Through a focus on performance-based interventions, the role of contemporary art in generating knowledge is emphasized, promoting critical reflection and connecting scientific research with aesthetic and experiential dimensions. Integrating technological innovation, artistic experimentation, and human-centered perspectives, the work contributes to a framework in which art becomes a means to explore the cognitive processes, social dynamics, and cultural implications of emerging technologies.

This approach aligns with the goals of interdisciplinary research programs, demonstrating how visual and performative practices can enrich both scientific understanding and artistic expression and offering new methodologies for collaborative, participatory, and experimental research.

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